

**NEW VARIATIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PERIODIC
WAVES IN THE FRACTIONAL KORTEWEG–DE VRIES
EQUATION**

FÁBIO NATALI

Periodic waves in the fractional Korteweg–de Vries equation have been previously characterized as constrained minimizers of energy subject to fixed momentum and mass. Here we characterize these periodic waves as constrained minimizers of the quadratic form of energy subject to fixed cubic part of energy and the zero mean. This new variational characterization allows us to unfold the existence region of travelling periodic waves and to give a sharp criterion for spectral stability of periodic waves with respect to perturbations of the same period. The sharp stability criterion is given by the monotonicity of the map from the wave speed to the wave momentum similarly to the stability criterion for solitary waves. This is a joint work with D. Pelinovsky (McMaster University) and U. Le (McMaster University).

UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DE MARINGÁ
Email address: `fmanatali@uem.br`